

Enhancement of Heat Transfer Rate in a Solar Flat Plate Collector using Twisted Tape and Wire Coiled Turbulators

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Abstract : Influences of insertion of wire coils in conjunction with twisted tapes on heat transfer and solar radiation without disturbing the flow inside the riser tubes in a solar water heater is experimentally investigated in this present work. The wire coil used as a turbulator is placed inside the riser tube while the twisted tape is inserted into the wire coil to create a continuous swirling flow along the tube wall. The results of the heat transfer have been compared well with the available results. The heat transfer rate in the collector has been found to be increased by 18% to 70%. Solar water heaters having inserts in the flow tubes perform better than the conventional plain ones. It has been observed that heat losses are reduced consequently increasing the thermal performance about 30% over the plain water heaters under the same operating conditions. The effect of twisted tape with wire coils, flow Reynolds number, and the intensity of solar radiation on the thermal performance of the solar water heater has been presented.

Keywords : Solar Flat Plate Collector, Heat Transfer, Twisted tape, Wire coiled turbulators

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014